

Changes in the Viscosity and Hydrogen Ion Concentration of some Inorganic Substances during the Process of Jelly Formation.

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In previous publications from these laboratories (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, **152**, 399 ; 1927, **164**, 63 ; 1927, **168**, 209) we have reported that jellies can be divided into three distinct groups. To the first group belong jellies of starch, gelatin, albumin, vanadium pentoxide, ceric hydroxide and blood clot. These jellies are, under suitable conditions, formed more or less instantaneously. Some of these jellies show the phenomenon of syneresis markedly. Jellies of iron, chromium and aluminium hydroxides belong to the second class and are probably formed by slow coagulation throughout the whole mass ; and von Weimarn jellies, as prepared from highly saturated solutions, belong to the third group. Moreover, our experimental results on viscosity measurements of colloids, especially of hydrophobic type, show that other things being identical, the uncharged substance is more hydrated than the sol, and greater the hydration of a substance, the greater will be its viscosity.

In order to throw light on the nature of jelly formation, we have measured the viscosity and hydrogen ion concentration during the process of gelation of several inorganic jellies. The viscosity measurements are recorded in the following tables.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ferric hydroxide jelly.

Ferric chloride (4 c. c. of $M/2$) was mixed with ammonium sulphate (1 c. c. of $2M$), sodium acetate (2 c. c. of $3.57N$) and water (12.5 c. c.). To the mixture was added ammonia (0.5 c. c. of $2.34N$) with constant stirring till a clear solution was obtained. This solution sets to an opaque jelly in 6 hours. Viscosities were found out at different intervals by Farrow's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **101**, 347). Temperature was maintained at 30° .

TABLE I.

Time in minutes :	0	30	60	90	107	132
Viscosity :	0·009324	0·009324	0·009349	0·01158	0·01731	0·01928

When log of viscosity is plotted against time, a curve is obtained which shows that during the first portion of the graph, viscosity does not markedly change with time, but after two hours there is an abrupt rise in viscosity.

Chromium hydroxide jelly.

To 4 c. c. of *M*/2-chromic chloride, 8 c. c. of 3·57*N*-sodium acetate were added. After half an hour, 2 c. c. of 2*N*-ammonium sulphate and 6 c. c. of 2·34*N*-ammonia were added drop by drop and total volume was made up to 20 c. c. The mixture sets to a jelly in 6½ hours. Viscosities were taken at 30°.

TABLE II.

Time in minutes :	0	30	60	90	120	150
Viscosity :	0·01465	0·01469	0·01527	0·01646	0·01873	0·02208

For the first two hours, there is very little change in viscosity but after that it varies exponentially with time, and during this period logarithms of viscosities plotted against time give almost a straight line. After five hours the mixture becomes highly viscous, and sets to a firm violet jelly in another hour.

Aluminium hydroxide jelly.

4 C. c. of *M*/2-aluminium nitrate were mixed with 2 c. c. of 3·17*N*-sodium acetate and 2 c. c. of 2*M*-ammonium sulphate. To the mixture, 1·3 c. c. of 2·34*N*-ammonia were added with constant stirring. Total volume was made up to 20 c. c. by adding requisite amount of water. This colourless solution sets to a white opaque jelly within 2½ hours. Viscosities were determined at 30°.

TABLE III.

Time in minutes :	0	30	45	60
Viscosity :	0·009480	0·009480	0·009786	0·011580

After an hour the mixture becomes highly viscous, and sets in another $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. When logarithms of viscosities are plotted against time, the graph obtained is a curve.

Stannic hydroxide jelly.

20 C. c. of 1.48*M*-stannic chloride were mixed with 3 c. c. of 3.57*N*-sodium acetate, 1.7 c. c. of *M*-ammonium sulphate and 1.70 c. c. of 0.96 *N*-ammonia, total volume being 26.4 c. c. This colourless mixture sets to a firm white opaque jelly in the course of five hours. Viscosities were determined during the course of gelation at 30°.

TABLE IV.

Time in minutes :	0	15	30	45
Viscosity ;	0.009186	0.009298	0.009515	0.009788
Time in minutes :	60	78	98	120
Viscosity :	0.01031	0.0110	0.01352	0.02387

When logarithms of viscosities are plotted against time, a straight line is obtained, and thus viscosity changes exponentially with time.

Mercuric oxide jelly.

Bunce (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1914, **18**, 269) obtained mercuric oxide jellies by mixing mercuric chloride solution with acetic caustic potash. 20 C. c. of 6.4% mercuric chloride solution were gradually mixed with 20 c. c. of 0.807*N*-acetic caustic potash solution which was prepared by dissolving about 22.5 gm. of caustic potash in 375 c. c. of water and 15 c. c. of acetone. The clear colourless solution sets to a white opaque jelly in 10 hours. Viscosities were determined at 30°.

TABLE V.

Time in minutes ;	0	17	30	50
Viscosity :	0.008483	0.008710	0.008910	0.009184
Time in minutes :	65	85	105	
Viscosity :	0.009828	0.01092	0.01486	

When logarithms of viscosities are plotted against time, a regular straight line is obtained in the beginning, but afterwards viscosities rise more abruptly,

Mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid jelly.

This jelly was obtained by dissolving freshly precipitated mercuric oxide (6.7 gm. HgO suspended in 100 c.c. of water) in 15.77% solution of sulphosalicylic acid. To 10 c.c. of sulphosalicylic acid were added 10 c.c. of water and 10 c.c. of mercuric oxide suspension. On stirring, a clear solution was obtained. This solution deposited a little precipitate during first five hours. This was filtered off and the clear filtrate set to a pinkish transparent jelly in 24 hours. Viscosities were recorded at 30°.

TABLE VI.

Time in hrs. & mins :	0	7/-	7/45	8/45
Viscosity :	0.008613	0.008973	0.009240	0.009290
Time in hrs. & mins. :	9/15	10/15	10/45	11/15
Viscosity :	0.009542	0.01209	0.01890	0.03483

After 11 hours the solution becomes highly viscous. There is no marked change in viscosity during first 6 hours. Then for another three hours, the graph obtained by plotting logarithms of viscosities against time is a straight line, but afterwards viscosities rise more abruptly.

Ferric arsenate jelly.

Grimaux (*Compt. rend.*, 1884, **98**, 1540), and Holmes (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **38**, 1970 ; 1919, **41**, 763) obtained a clear red jelly by dialysing solutions of ferric arsenate peptised by ferric chloride. 100 C.c. of about 1.5 N-solution of ferric chloride were mixed with 40 c.c. of 18% potassium arsenate solution, and the mixture was dialysed for 4 days. The sol on heating in a platinum crucible gave 44.8 gm. Fe₂O₃/ litre.

To 30 c.c. of this ferric arsenate sol were added 3.75 c.c. of N/10-potassium sulphate. This mixture sets to a firm transparent red jelly in course of 4 days. Viscosities were taken at 30°.

TABLE VII.

Time in hrs. & mins :	0	0/26	0/56	1/23	2/0	
Viscosity :	0.01507	0.01540	0.01603	0.01664	0.01689	
Time in hrs. & mins. :	2/23	3/0	22/26	23/30	26/10	72/0
Viscosity :	0.01719	0.01746	0.02620	0.02682	0.02863	0.1049

When logarithms of viscosities are plotted against time, a regular straight line is obtained from the very beginning and is maintained for a long interval of time.

Ferric phosphate jelly.

Holmes (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **38**, 1970) has observed that when a sol obtained by peptising ferric phosphate with ferric chloride is dialysed, a red transparent gel is obtained. We have obtained a clear sol by dialysing a mixture of $M/2$ -ferric chloride solution, and 22% potassium phosphate (KH_2PO_4) solution in ratio of 2 to 1 by volume, which sets to a red clear jelly on addition of potassium sulphate. 15 C.c. of the sol containing 46 gm. of ferric phosphate per litre, were mixed with 1.2 c.c. of $N/4$ -potassium sulphate. Viscosities were taken at 30° .

TABLE VIII.

Time in minutes :	0	40	80	130	185	252
Viscosity :	0.01859	0.02159	0.02648	0.03176	0.03876	0.04957

After five hours, the sol becomes very viscous, though it completely sets in 36 hours. When logarithms of viscosities are plotted against time, a straight line is obtained, showing that viscosity is varying exponentially with time.

Ferric molybdate jelly.

We have observed that when potassium molybdate solution is added to ferric chloride solution, a precipitate is obtained which disappears on shaking. If this clear solution be allowed to stand, it develops opalescence, and finally an opaque yellow gel is obtained. To 8 c.c. of $M/2.69$ -ferric chloride solution were added 4 c.c. of water and 8 c.c. of 10% potassium molybdate solution. The mixture sets to a gel in 10 hours. Viscosities were taken at 30° .

TABLE IX.

Time in minutes :	0	15	32	46	68
Viscosity :	0.009966	0.01009	0.01029	0.01052	0.01094
Time in minutes :	98	128	158	188	300
Viscosity :	0.01233	0.01442	0.01918	0.03526	0.10620

When logarithms of viscosities are plotted against time, an interesting curve is obtained. The first portion of the curve (up to 68 minutes) is a straight line with less slope. Then for another one and half hours, another straight line of a deeper slope is obtained. In the third portion of the curve, viscosity changes are more abrupt.

Chromium arsenate jelly.

Holmes (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **38**, 1980) observed that a colloidal solution of chromium arsenate, peptised by chromic chloride, sets to a firm green transparent jelly on continued dialysis. We prepared a clear sol by adding 1 part by volume of 18% potassium arsenate solution to 3 parts of about $M/2$ -chromic chloride solution, and dialysing it for 5 days. The sol contained 35 gm. Cr_2O_3 per litre. 20 C.c. of this sol were mixed with 2 c.c. of $N/100$ -potassium sulphate which sets to a clear jelly in three days.

TABLE X.

Time in hrs. & mins :	1/0	1/44	2/29	3/20	4/16	4 1/2-
Viscosity :	0.02551	0.02740	0.02945	0.03267	0.03595	0.6080

The change in viscosity with time is fairly exponential for sufficient interval. The graph obtained by plotting logarithms of viscosity against time for the first five hours is a straight line.

Stannic tungstate jelly.

8 C.c. of stannic chloride solution (1.35 M) were mixed with 2 c.c. of water and 14 c.c. of 15% sodium tungstate solution. The mixture sets to a firm white jelly in the course of 10 hours. Viscosities were taken at 30°.

TABLE XI.

Time in mins :	0	90	125	168	210	245	283
Viscosity :	0.01349	0.01570	0.01640	0.01691	0.01807	0.02015	0.02230

The graph obtained by plotting logarithms of viscosities against time is a straight line for first four hours and then viscosities rise more abruptly.

Stannic molybdate jelly.

1·5M-stannic chloride solution was mixed with 25% potassium molybdate solution below the precipitation value and the mixture was allowed to dialyse for two days. A clear transparent sol was obtained. With 5 c.c. of this sol were mixed 5 c.c. of water. The mixture sets to a jelly within 5 hours. Concentration of the sol = 91·04 gm. SnO₂/ litre.

Change in viscosity during gelation was recorded by Ostwald's viscosimeter at 25°. Viscosity of water at 25° is 0·00893.

TABLE XII.

Time in minutes :	0	3	5	19	20
Viscosity :	0·01272	0·01353	0·01471	0·01804	0·02300
Time in minutes :	30	40	60	80	
Viscosity :	0·03032	0·03447	0·04412	0·07505	

When logarithms of viscosities are plotted against time, a straight line is obtained. After one and half hours, the sol becomes highly viscous.

Ferric borate jelly.

To M/2·69-ferric chloride solution, a saturated solution of borax was added below the precipitation point with constant stirring. A red clear sol was obtained after dialysing the solution for 30 days. The sol contained 11·78 gm. of ferric borate per litre. To 18 c.c. of this sol, 1·4 c.c. of water and 0·6 c.c. of N/10-potassium chloride were added and viscosities were taken during gelation. The mixture sets to a jelly in 8 hours. Viscosities were recorded by Farrow's method at 30°.

TABLE XIII.

Time in minutes :	0	23	56	90
Viscosity :	0·01210	0·01559	0·02072	0·02720

The graph obtained by plotting logarithms of viscosity against time is a straight line.

Thorium phosphate jelly.

To 10 c.c. of thorium nitrate solution (12·035 g. in 250 c.c.) were added 1·6 c.c. of 22% potassium phosphate solution and the mixture

was well-shaken. The solution becomes very viscous within a short period. Viscosities were measured by Ostwald's viscosimeter at 25°.

Time of flow for water at 25° = 99 seconds, and viscosity of water at 25° = 0.00899.

TABLE XIV.

Time in minutes.	Time of flow.	Viscosity.
0	375 seconds.	0.03383
9	988 seconds.	0.08914
27	More than 2½ hours.	—

The mixture sets to a transparent jelly in 6 hours.

Thorium molybdate jelly.

10 C. c. of thorium nitrate solution (12.035 gm. in 250 c.c.) were mixed with 0.8 c.c. of water and 1.2 c.c. of 3% potassium molybdate solution. The mixture sets to a transparent jelly in 23 hours, though it becomes highly viscous within one hour. Viscosities were measured by Ostwald's viscosimeter at 25°.

TABLE XV.

Time in minutes :	0	5	9	15	25
Viscosity :	0.02030	0.02517	0.02950	0.03915	0.05170
Time in minutes :	40	55	79		
Viscosity :	0.07560	0.11840	0.26960		

The graph obtained by plotting logarithms of viscosities against time is fairly a straight line for a sufficient period.

Thorium arsenate jelly.

10 C.c. of thorium nitrate solution (12.035 gms. in 250 c.c.) were mixed with 0.65 c.c. of 18% potassium arsenate solution and 1.35 c.c. of water. The mixture sets to a transparent jelly with slight opalescence in 3 hours. Viscosities were measured by Ostwald's viscosimeter at 30°.

TABLE XVI.

Time in minutes :	0	15	40	60	70
Viscosity :	0.008806	0.009670	0.01088	0.01442	0.01770
Time in minutes :	80	90	100	120	140
Viscosity :	0.02253	0.026253	0.03022	0.03902	0.11920

When logarithms of viscosities are plotted against time, the graph is a straight line between the first and second hours. There is very little change in the viscosity in the beginning, while in the third hour the viscosity changes abruptly.

Our results on viscosity measurements generally show three stages in gelation :

- (i) In the first stage, there is very little change in viscosity with time.
- (ii) In the second stage, there is regular exponential change with time.
- (iii) In the third stage, viscosity goes on increasing abruptly till a jelly is formed.

The first stage corresponds to the region when true electrolytic solution passes to the colloidal condition, *i.e.*, colloidal condition is not at once attained after mixing the solutions, and it takes some time during which period there is very little change in viscosity. Jellies of iron, chromium, and aluminium hydroxides as well as that of mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid exhibit this stage markedly.

In the second stage, the mixture has attained colloidal condition, and there is regular exponential change in viscosity due to the gradual charge neutralisation and thus increase in hydration. Dialysed sols of chromium arsenate, ferric arsenate, phosphate and borate, and stannic molybdate do not show the first stage because here we initially start with the colloids obtained by dialysis, and the addition of slight trace of coagulating electrolyte, from the very beginning, causes regular decrease in charge and corresponding increase in hydration. Thus in these jellies, viscosities vary strictly exponentially for a great length of time, and fair straight lines are obtained when values for logarithms of viscosities are plotted against time. At the end of the second stage, viscosity changes are more abrupt, and there is a sudden rise in the curve. This stage is really where the formation of specific structure of jellies takes place. Sometimes the second

and the third stages are mixed up, and in these cases a regular curve is obtained—as in the case of iron and aluminium hydroxides—even when logarithms of viscosities are plotted against time. Kugelmass ("Colloid Symposium Monograph", 1925, 3, 195) has studied the changes in viscosity in the course of coagulation or clotting of blood. The viscosity was found to increase very slowly at first, then at the point of clot indication vary rapidly till a maximum was reached.

The changes in hydrogen ion concentration during gelation are recorded below.

Ferric hydroxide jelly.

In the case of iron and some other jellies, the use of quinhydrone electrode was found more suitable than Hildebrand's hydrogen electrode. The jelly-forming solution was mixed with a little quinhydrone (about 50-100 mg.) and the electrode used was a bright piece of platinum foil. The electromotive force developed against a N-KCl/calomel electrode was measured by vernier potentiometer (Scientific Instrument Co., Cambridge). The following expression of Kolthoff (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1925, 144, 259) was used for the calculation of p_H values.

$$p_H = \frac{0.4181 - 0.0005(t-18) - E}{0.0577 + 0.0002(t-18)}$$

where t is the temperature and E , the electromotive force developed against N-KCl/calomel electrode.

The following solutions were mixed as in the viscosity experiments:—

M/2-Ferric chloride	...	6 c.c.
2.84 N-Sodium acetate	...	3.75 c.c.
2M-Ammonium sulphate	...	1.5 c.c.
4.26 N-Ammonia	...	0.45 c.c.
Total volume	...	30 c.c.
Time for gelation	...	6 hours.

TABLE XVII.

Time in mins.	E. M. F.	p_H	c_H	Diminution in e_H .	% Diminution in c_H .
0	0.248	2.91	1.23×10^{-3}		
15	0.239	3.06	0.87	..	
30	0.230	3.22	0.602	..	
45	0.228	3.26	0.549	..	0.681×10^{-3}
60	0.228	3.26	0.549	..	55.3
120	0.228	3.26	0.549	..	

Chromium hydroxide jelly.

M/2-Chromium chloride	...	4 c.c.
3.57 N-Sodium acetate	...	8 c.c.
2M-Ammonium sulphate	...	2 c.c.
2.34 N-ammonia	...	6 c.c.
Total volume	...	20 c.c.
Time for jelly formation	...	7 hours.

TABLE XVIII.

Hydrogen electrode and N-KCl/calomel electrode were used.

Time in mins.	E. M. F.	p_H	c_H	Diminution in c_H .	% Diminution in c_H .
0	0.578	4.96	1.096×10^{-5}		
5	0.597	5.28	5.25	..	
30	0.599	5.31	0.490	..	0.615×10^{-5}
45	0.599	5.31	0.490	..	56.6
180	0.5996	5.32	0.479	..	

Aluminium hydroxide jelly.

M/2-Aluminium nitrate	...	4 c.c.
2M-Ammonium sulphate	...	2 c.c.
3.57 N-Sodium acetate	...	2 c.c.
2.34 N-Ammonia	...	1.3 c.c.
Total volume	...	20 c.c.
Time for jelly formation	...	3 hours.

TABLE XIX.

Hydrogen electrode and N-KCl/calomel electrode were used.

Time in mins.	E. M. F.	p_H	c_H	Diminution in c_H .	% Diminution in c_H .
0	0.4670	3.082	0.328×10^{-3}		
30	0.4950	3.550	0.382	,	
45	0.510	3.810	0.155	..	0.673×10^{-3}
60	0.510	3.810	0.155	,	81
75	0.510	3.810	0.155	..	

Ferric molybdate jelly

M/2 Ferric chloride	...	10 c c
10% Potassium molybdate		8 c c
Water		2 c c
Time for jelly formation		7 hours.

Quinhydrone and N KCl/calomel electrodes were used

TABLE XX.

Time in minutes	E M F	p_{H}	c_{H}	Diminution in c_{H}	% Diminution in c_{H}
0	0.115	5.20	6.31×10^{-5}		
10	0.095	5.54	2.89 ,,	4.12×10^{-5}	65.3
30	0.088	5.66	2.19 ,,		
60	0.088	5.66	2.19 ,,		

Thorium arsenate jelly

Thorium nitrate, 12.035 gm /250 c c	.	10 c c
Potassium arsenate, 18% solution	...	0.4 c c
Water	...	1.6 c c.
Time of jelly formation		3 hours

Quinhydrone and N-KCl/calomel electrodes were used

TABLE XXI

Time in minutes	E M F.	p_{H}	c_{H}	Diminution in c_{H}	% Diminution in c_{H}
0	0.341	1.31	0.490×10^{-1}		
10	0.340	1.33	0.468 ,,		
20	0.339	1.34	0.457 ,,	0.054×10^{-1}	11
30	0.338	1.36	0.436 ,,		
60	0.338	1.36	0.436 ,,		

Thorium phosphate jelly.

Thorium nitrate, 12.035 gm./250 c.c.	...	10 c.c.
Potassium phosphate, 22% solution	...	0.5 c.c.
Water	...	1.5 c.c.
Time for gelation	...	3 hours.

Quinhydrone and N-KCl/calomel electrodes were used.

TABLE XXII.

Time in minutes.	E.M.F.	p_H	c_H	Diminution in c_H .	% Diminution in c_H .
0	0.343	1.27	0.537×10^{-1}		
10	0.3395	1.33	0.468	..	
20	0.3375	1.37	0.426	..	0.121×10^{-1} 22.4
30	0.3370	1.38	0.416	..	
60	0.3370	1.38	0.416	..	

Thorium molybdate jelly.

Thorium nitrate, 12.035 gms./250 c.c.	...	10 c.c.
Potassium molybdate, 3% solution	...	2 c.c.
Time for jelly formation	...	5½ hours.

Quinhydrone and N-KCl/calomel electrodes were used.

TABLE XXIII.

Time in minutes.	E.M.F.	p_H	c_H	Diminution in c_H .	% Diminution in c_H .
0	0.291	2.16	0.692×10^{-2}		
20	0.283	2.30	0.501	..	
35	0.280	2.34	0.457	..	0.235×10^{-2} 41.2
45	0.2792	2.37	0.427	..	
70	0.282	2.39	0.407	..	
80	0.282	2.39	0.407	..	

Stannic tungstate jelly.

M/1'099-Stannic chloride	...	10 c.c.
10% Sodium tungstate solution	...	10 c.c.
Time for jelly formation	...	10 hours.

Hydrogen electrode and N/10-KCl/calomel electrode were used.

TABLE XXIV.

Time in minutes.	E.M.F.	p_{H}	c_{H}	Diminution in c_{H} .	% Diminution in c_{H} .
0	0'3896	0'907	$1'24 \times 10^{-1}$		
5	0'3344	0'988	1'03 ..		
10	0'3954	1'021	0'953 ..	$0'379 \times 10^{-1}$	32'6
20	0'3980	1'049	0'893 ..		
30	0'3990	1'065	0'861 ..		
60	0'3990	1'065	0'861 ..		

Stannic phosphate jelly.

M/1'048-Stannic chloride	...	10 c.c.
22% Potassium phosphate	...	6'6 c.c.
Total volume	...	20 c.c.
Time of gelation	...	2 hours.

Hydrogen electrode and N-KCl/calomel electrode were used.

TABLE XXV.

Time in minutes.	E.M.F.	p_{H}	c_{H}	Diminution in c_{H} .	% Diminution in c_{H} .
0	0'2990	0'240	$5'75 \times 10^{-1}$		
7	0'3003	0'262	5'47 ..		
30	0'3112	0'446	3'58 ..	$2'17 \times 10^{-1}$	37'7
50	0'3112	0'446	3'58 ..		

Stannic arsenate jelly.

M/1.048-Stannic chloride	...	10 c.c.
18% Potassium arsenate solution	...	10 c.c.
Time of gelation	...	1 hour.

TABLE XXVI.

Hydrogen electrode and N/KCl-calomel electrode were used.

Time in minutes.	E.M.F.	p_H	c_H	Diminution in c_H .	% Diminution in c_H .
0	0.2297	0.220	6.03×10^{-4}		
10	0.300	0.257	5.54 ..	0.49×10^{-4}	8
30	0.300	0.257	5.54 ..		

The foregoing results show that in many cases there is considerable decrease in the hydrogen ion concentration on gelation. In some cases the decrease comes up to 50% of the original hydrogen ion concentration. It has been observed by Kugelmass (*loc. cit.*, p. 160) that during blood clotting the hydrogen ion concentration changes continuously, and the rate of diminution of hydrogen ion concentration is great at the first interval but it gradually falls off approaching zero, *i.e.*, an asymptotic limit. It has been also observed that the higher the initial hydrogen ion concentration, the greater the diminution in c_H after clotting. By starting with solutions of

different initial hydrogen ion concentrations, the diminution in hydrogen ions was found to be 50 ± 10 . Our results give average diminution in most cases to be 50 ± 20 . The influence of hydrogen ions on the formation of jellies has been studied by Kraemer ("Colloid Symposium," Wisconsin, 1923, 1, 62) in the case of manganese arsenate jellies. Tarr (*Dela. agri. expt. sta. Bull.*, 1923, 134, Tech. 2) has observed that for minimum point of jelly formation, p_H 3.40

must be obtained whether mineral or organic acids are used in preparation of fruit jellies if pectin and sugar contents are kept constant.

According to the transparency, jellies may be divided into three classes:—

(a) Perfectly transparent jellies, which retain their transparency for a long time, *e.g.*, arsenates of zinc, manganese, iron(*ic*), chromium

and thorium, phosphates of iron and thorium; and other jellies as of mercuri sulphosalicylic acid

(b) Transparent jellies with some opalescence at the point of setting but opacity increasing with time and finally during the course of a few hours forming perfectly opaque firm jellies, e.g., stannic tungstate, borate, phosphate molybdate and arsenate jellies

(c) Clear sols, developing opalescence and finally at the point of setting they become perfectly opaque e.g. ferric molybdate ferric tungstate hydroxides of iron tin aluminium and chromium

Von Weimarn jellies which are precipitated from the highly concentrated solutions are also transparent in the beginning but after a few minutes they become perfectly opaque. From the transparency of jellies it may be concluded that the process of gelation is accompanied by (i) increase in the hydration or the adsorption of the solvent and (ii) the growth of particles. When the first factor is alone taking part in gelation transparent jellies are obtained. For example when some coagulating electrolyte such as potassium sulphate is added to ferric arsenate sol charge neutralisation begins but the same forces which bring out the agglomeration of these uncharged particles cause them to adsorb the solvent medium and thus instead of precipitation jelly elements are formed which may give rise to either gelatinous precipitates (if the coagulating electrolyte is in excess) or jellies under suitable conditions. These jellies are perfectly transparent.

In case of jellies of second class growth of particles begins after the setting of jellies. Some of the residual forces which remain after hydration and adsorption of solvent bring out the agglomeration of some particles after gelation and thus, finally, perfectly opaque jelly is formed.

In other jellies where sol develops opacity from the very beginning before setting growth of particles and hydration tendency develop side by side and only opaque jellies are obtained. These jellies have the weakest texture while the jellies of the first class are most firm.

Thus, on neutralisation of the charge, the tendency of particles is either to agglomerate or to hydrate. When there is agglomeration alone, precipitation occurs, when hydration is slight and agglomeration predominant, gelatinous precipitate is formed, and when hydration predominates over agglomeration, opaque or opalescent jellies are formed, and when agglomeration is negligible

in comparison with hydration, transparent jellies are formed which maintain their transparency for a long time.

It may be stated that addition of excess of coagulating electrolytes to jelly forming sols always helps agglomeration, and this is why even the transparent jellies formed by excessive addition of electrolytes synerise very rapidly.

It has been shown by Freundlich and Seifriz (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, **108**, 153) that those sols which display deviations from Poiseuille's law exhibit marked elasticity, and moreover these sols consist of non-spherical particles. It appears that for the formation of a net-work or mesh which has been ascribed to be so necessary for holding water or any other medium, non-spherical particles are essential because these offer the maximum surface for adsorption or hydration.

Increase of temperature also helps the growth of particles and perhaps the tendency of hydration is also accelerated to some extent, and for this reason, jelly is more readily formed at higher temperatures. A sol of tin molybdate containing 91.04 gm. of SnO₂/litre obtained by dialysing a solution of stannic chloride and potassium molybdate for 24 hours, sets to jelly at various temperatures in different times when half diluted.

TABLE XXVIII.

Temp.	...	90°	70°	60°	50°	40°	24°
Time of setting (min.)	...	1	2	4	7	20	6 hrs.

On warming the clear jelly-forming-sol in a water-bath at a higher temperature, say 80°, the sol develops turbidity, and finally an opaque or translucent jelly is obtained. It can be seen with naked eyes even that turbidity begins at first near the surface, and before setting of the jelly, it is not spread *uniformly* throughout the solution. In spite of this, a jelly is formed, which is in contradiction to the views held by Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1923, **27**, 685; 1922, **26**, 429) that for gelation uniform precipitation throughout the solution is necessary. Weiser has also laid much emphasis on rapid and uniform mixing of the jelly-forming constituents. This factor does not appear to be of much importance, and perhaps is only applicable to pseudo-jellies in which hydration tendency is not so marked and perhaps the setting is due to a

sort of release of supersaturation, as in the case of copper hydroxide prepared from copper acetate and ammonia.

The phenomenon of syneresis is also an important property of some jellies and is best exhibited in the case of zirconium hydroxide, ceric hydroxide, vanadium pentoxide and in the clotting of blood. The jelly of ferric borate or phosphate also undergoes marked syneresis if the coagulating electrolyte is in excess. In reality, syneresis is due to the shrinkage of the hydrated mass. Addition of excess of electrolyte in coagulating the sol gradually accelerates agglomeration and diminishes the hydration and thus shortly after setting the jelly, the excess of electrolyte brings about the syneresis. But the phenomenon of syneresis is not a general rule with all jellies. As has already been said, excessive coagulating electrolytes cause syneresis, and if still more coagulating electrolyte be used, jelly will not set at all and the whole will be precipitated. Thus there are four limits within which the function of electrolyte is restricted:

(i) Up to a certain limit—no jelly formation.

(ii) Up to the second limit—stable jellies undergoing no marked syneresis.

(iii) Between second and third limits—Firm jellies readily synerising.

(iv) Above the third limit—no jelly formation, simply precipitation.

Summary.

1. The changes in viscosity with time during the process of gelation have been determined in the case of various jellies. When logarithms of viscosities are plotted against time, straight lines are obtained for a sufficient length of time in the case of chromium hydroxide, stannic hydroxide, mercuric oxide, mercuri-sulpho-salicylic acid, ferric arsenate, ferric phosphate, chromium arsenate, stannic tungstate, stannic molybdate, ferric borate, thorium molybdate, and thorium arsenate jellies. It shows that the gelation is a continuous process. The viscosity-changes are complex in gelation of ferric hydroxide and aluminium hydroxide.

2. In most cases, three stages have been observed during gelation, the first stage corresponding to very little change in viscosity, the second stage where viscosity changes exponentially with time, and the third stage where changes are abrupt.

3. During the process of gelation, diminution of hydrogen ion concentrations averaging to 50 ± 20 per cent. of the original has been observed.

4. Jellies have been classified according to transparency and explained on the basis of hydration and agglomeration of the particles.

5. A mechanism of the phenomenon of syneresis has also been suggested.

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